

MODERN INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES: FEATURES AND DIRECTIONS OF ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8004536>

Abstract The relevance of the chosen topic lies in the fact that today information occupies a special position in the economy. Information is one of the main, decisive factors that determines the development of technology and resources in general. The use of electronic computers and personal computers led to a radical transformation of relations and technological foundations of activities in the economic sphere. At present, the dissemination of information in the information sector of the economy cannot be imagined without the use of new information technologies. Without them, the economy of both individual enterprises and the whole state will remain among the lagging behind. The purpose of the article is to determine the significance of the development of information technology (IT).

Keywords: Information, Informatization, Information Protection, individual documents, individual arrays, funds, data banks, natural resource, labor, capital.

The information economy has changed many aspects of economic reality, including the function of money, which gradually turned from a universal equivalent of labor costs into a means of payment. Virtual banks and payment systems are the fruit of the development of information technology. In the economy and business, information technologies are used for processing, sorting and aggregating data, for organizing the interaction of participants in the process and computer technology, for meeting information needs, for operational communication.

Thus, the development of computer technology, information and communication technologies, the creation and distribution of the global Internet, indeed, open up unprecedented opportunities for using information.

Economists consider information as information in the field of the economy that must be recorded, transmitted, stored and processed for use in managing both the economy of the country as a whole and its individual objects. Information allows you to get a decision on how to organize the production of goods and services more efficiently and cost-effectively. Economic information is directly related to the management of groups of people, the production, distribution and consumption of material goods and services. It includes information about the composition of labor, material and financial resources and the state of control objects at a certain moment. Information acquires the features of an economic good and is circulated in the economy as a resource used in the process of economic activity, as well as a product (information goods, services.)

With the help of information products, the consumer has the opportunity to satisfy the need for new information and knowledge, as well as various aesthetic needs. Information goods and services include software, databases, educational services, and consulting [1]. In the process of creating information goods, the main means of production is intelligence, which is the ability of a person to create new knowledge. As a result of intellectual activity, a unique product is created that brings income to its creator in the process of replication (distribution

of material carriers with created information) or materialization in goods, means of production, technologies.

For the first time, a fairly clear definition of the concept of "information resources" was formulated in the State Law "On Information, Informatization and Information Protection" [3]. This law provides the following definition: "Information resources - individual documents and individual arrays of documents in information systems (libraries, archives, funds, data banks, other information systems)". Documents and arrays of information referred to in this law do not exist by themselves. They represent in different forms the knowledge possessed by the people who created them. As an economic resource, information has a number of features that distinguish it from traditional factors of production - land (natural resources), labor, capital. We note the main ones that radically distinguish information from other products.

1) Information does not disappear when consumed, but can be used repeatedly. An information product retains the information it contains, no matter how many times it has been used.

2) The information product is subject to a kind of "obsolescence" over time. Although information does not wear out with use, it can lose its value as the knowledge it provides is no longer relevant.

3) Different consumers of information goods and services are comfortable with different ways of providing information, because the consumption of an information product requires effort. This manifests such a property of information as addressing it to a specific group of consumers.

4) The production of information, in contrast to the production of material goods, requires significant costs compared to the costs of replication. Copying this or that information product costs, as a rule, much cheaper than its production. This property of the information product - the difficulty of production and the relative ease of replication - creates, in particular, many problems in connection with the definition of property rights within the scope of information activity.

Information as an economic resource is used in various directions. Among the main areas, the following should be highlighted:

- commercialization of information in goods, services, technologies (creation of science-intensive products, intellectual goods, information services, development of new production and management technologies, etc.);
- impact on subjective perceptions and expectations of economic entities. Examples include creating an information image of a product, a company (reputation), creating needs or influencing them [4].

Thus, from an economic point of view, information is a strategic resource, one of the main resources for increasing the productivity of an enterprise. Information is the basis of an entrepreneur's maneuver with matter and energy, since it is information that allows you to set the strategic goals and objectives of the enterprise and use the opportunities that open up; make informed and timely management decisions; coordinate the actions of various departments, directing their efforts to achieve common goals.

Information has real value due to its structure. The existence of a number of properties of information similar to those of traditional resources has given rise to the use of many economic characteristics (price, cost, costs, profits, etc.) in the analysis of information

production. As an economic resource, information is intended for exchange, is available in limited quantities, and effective demand is presented for it.

The value, or usefulness, of information lies in the ability to give additional freedom of action to the consumer. Information expands the set of possible alternatives and helps to correctly assess their consequences. Information resources are the product of the information system, since the information system is an interconnected set of tools, methods and personnel used to store, process and issue information in order to achieve the goal [5].

Today, information technology can make a decisive contribution to strengthening the relationship between the growth of labor productivity, output, investment and employment. New types of services distributed through networks are able to create many jobs, which is confirmed by the practice of recent years. Modern IT, with its rapidly growing potential and rapidly decreasing costs, opens up great opportunities for new forms of work organization and employment within both individual corporations and society as a whole.

Thus, the development of the information technology market will be facilitated by:

- * the introduction of information technologies in the socio-economic sphere and public administration;
- * the development of domestic production in the field of information and communication technologies, including the implementation of a set of software solutions for the development of microelectronics;
- * the revitalization of the situation in the information technology market through the implementation of priority national projects, as well as sectoral and regional development strategies;
- * stimulating the development of the information technology market, including the creation of technology parks in the field of high technologies.
- * the promotion of Uzbek enterprises in the field of information and communication technologies to the world market, strengthening of Uzbekistan's position in international industry organizations;
- * the implementation of tax and customs policy measures aimed at stimulating organizations operating in the field of information technology.

In Uzbekistan, the information technology sector is currently much less developed than in many developed countries of the world. This hinders the further development of the Uzbek economy. Because of this, studies of many economic aspects of the development of this sector are especially relevant for our country. Trends in the development of innovation processes in Uzbekistan, including information technology, will determine the country's place in the world economic system in the future. For the development of the Uzbek economy, it is necessary to provide favorable conditions for the development of the IT sector. This can be achieved both with the active support of the sector by the state, and by attracting significant investment in the sector from various sources.

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